

Implementation of an Intelligent Model in Comparison with the Double Inclusion and the Finite Element Methods to Predict the Mechanical Properties of Polyethylene Bio loaded by Snail Shell Particles

Communication Info

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Keywords:

Bio-loading

Bio composites

Intelligent model

Finite element method

Double inclusion model

Abstract

Modern scientific investigations have focused on the experimental and computational modeling of the mechanical characteristics of bio composites. This is to identify more answers to the environmental, ecological, and long-term development constraints that bio composites can address [1]. The matrix in this numerical study is polypropylene, which is one of the most widely used polymers in today's industry due to its low cost, availability, and interesting thermomechanical properties, and which has applications in transportation, infrastructure, packaging, home applications, and the automotive industry, among others. The bio load employed is snail shell particles, which are chemically comparable to calcium carbonates CaCO_3 and have been overlooked by researchers in terms of bio composites. In comparison to the Finite element and Mori-Tanaka models, a sophisticated neural network model [2] was able to predict the mechanical properties of the polymer reinforced with Snail Shell particles. The results showed that bio loading with snail shell particles improved the mechanical characteristics of the bio composite under study. As a result, these particles demonstrate that they can be used to replace traditional loads in order to suit industrial needs, particularly in the reinforcing of polymers.

References

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